

AUTHORITY

Title	American Book Publishing Record
Author	R. R. Bowker
Publisher	Grey House Publishing
1st Edition	1960
Latest Edition	2018(Vol.60)
Language	English
Frequency	Monthly & Cumulative Annual

INTRODUCTION

American book publishing record is a current bibliographical source which provides a complete list of the books published and distributed in the U.S. It is a monthly publication from Grey House Publishing. The ABPR was earlier published by Bowker, but now it has been taken over by Grey House Publication. ABPR provides access to newest cataloguing records. It provides accurate and up to date information to the libraries about the list of books published in united states. It also provides detailed information about the books including the publishers of the books and their addresses etc. The annual ABPR published in march is compiled from the 12 monthly issues.

SCOPE

- ❖ A new edition every month ensures access to the latest information.
- ❖ Its annual edition covers approximately 50,000 entries of books published or distributed in the united states in 2018.
- ❖ Each edition contains MARC data received from the Library of Congress. Entries that are excluded are federal and other governmental publications, subscription books, dissertations (unless published), and journals and pamphlets under 49 pages. Pamphlets are included if we feel that the subject matter is current and topical or important enough to be of interest to the public.
- ❖ It's a trade bibliography which aims publicize the document of various publishers.
- ❖ There are two volumes for *Annual Cumulative* edition of *ABPR*.
 - Volume 1 contains Dewey range 000— Computer science, information & general works to 600—Technology.
 - Volume 2 contains Dewey range 700—Arts & recreation to 900—History & geography, Adult Fiction, Juvenile Fiction, Author and Title Indexes, and Subject Guide.

TREATMENT

➤ In ABPR entries includes the following bibliographic details:

- title (in italics)
- added title
- subtitle
- author statement
- edition statement
- publication place
- publisher
- publication date
- copyright date
- collation
- series statement(s) general note
- contents note
- bibliographic note
- Dewey Numbers
- LC Classification Numbers

- LC Control Number
 - subject tracings
 - ISBN
 - binding
 - price
- The Subject Headings in this edition of ABPR Annual Cumulative edition reflect the changes and additions of those in the 23rd edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification Schedule.
 - Each edition contains MARC records for over 10,000 new titles.

ARRANGEMENT

- ❖ Arranged into 3 easy to use parts: entries are arranged acc. to
 - Dewey Decimal Classification Number
 - Adult Fiction
 - Juvenile Fiction
- ❖ Further entries are arranged alphabetically acc. to authors name.
- ❖ Author index, title index and subject guide allows for immediate location of data.

FORMATE

- ❖ ABPR is available only in print format.
- ❖ Soft cover binding.
- ❖ Good quality paper.
- ❖ Clear and legible print.
- ❖ Three columns per page.
- ❖ Its annual edition is in two volumes.

SPECIAL FEATURES

- ❖ There is 'How to use' the ABPR.

DRAWBACK

- It is not available online.
- It is also not available in CD-ROM version.

CONCLUSION

The American Book Publishing Record is a bibliographical database which contains a list of American publications. ABPR keeps libraries, publishers, researcher's etc. abreast of the catalogued information. American Book Publishing Record is the cornerstone reference for cataloguing information for libraries of all sizes. Its monthly edition is most accurate and up to date tools on bibliographic information for the users and hence should be acquired by all the libraries interested in getting information on the books being published in U.S.

REFERENCES:

- <https://www.greyhouse.com/American-Book-Publishing-Record-Annual>
- <https://www.greyhouse.com/American-Book-Publishing-Record-Monthly>

Department of Library and Information Science

PUNJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH

ASSIGNMENT

OF

Information Sources and Services (PR.)

Topic: AMERICAN BOOK PUBLISHING RECORD

SUBMITTED TO:

Prof. Preeti Mahajan

SUBMITTED BY:

Anita Rani

M. Lib -1st sem.

Preface

The annual editions of the **American Book Publishing Record®** represent the accumulation of the twelve (12) monthly issues of *ABPR*. For this 2018 edition, approximately 50,000 entries are represented for books published or distributed in the United States.

The main input source is *MARC* data received from the Library of Congress. Entries that are excluded are federal and other governmental publications, subscription books, dissertations (unless published), and journals and pamphlets under 49 pages. Pamphlets are included if we feel that the subject matter is current and topical or important enough to be of interest to the public.

Entries include the following elements when they are available: *title* (in *italics*), added title, subtitle, author statement, edition statement, publication place, publisher, publication date, copyright date, collation, series statement(s) general note, contents note, bibliographic note, Dewey Numbers, LC Classification Numbers, LC Control Number, subject tracings, ISBN, binding, and price. For acquisitions information to be as current and comprehensive as possible we have obtained additional price and distribution information from the Books In Print database.

Entries are updated with corrections obtained from the Library of Congress. This includes CIP entries which are updated to complete entries.

The Subject Headings in this edition of *ABPR* Annual Cumulative edition reflect the changes and additions of those in the 22th edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification Schedule.

The format of entries reflects the ISBD (M) format with some modification. Briefly, the ISBD format divides the monographic bibliographic description into seven areas: (1) title and statement of authorship, (2) edition, (3) imprint, (4) collation, (5) series, (6) notes, and (7) ISBN. Binding and price are not divided by the conventional period-space-dash-space (-). Additionally, the ISBN, binding, and price have been positioned after the Library of Congress Classification Number(s), secondary Dewey Numbers (if present), and Control Number.

Some entries will also reflect some changes outlined by AACR2 cataloging rules with some modifications. For example, corporate authors as main entries will not have the spacing dividing the number, date, and location. The location will sometimes appear as added entry information.

There are two volumes for this edition of *ABPR* Annual Cumulative. Volume 1 contains Dewey range 000—Computer science, information & general works to 600—Technology. Volume 2 contains Dewey range 700—Arts & recreation to 900—History & geography, Adult Fiction, Juvenile Fiction, Author and Title Indexes, and Subject Guide.